

22IEM05 NEWSTAND

D8: Good practice guides for using the new transfer standard sources for spectral irradiance in the ultraviolet-visible-near infrared (UV-VIS-NIR) spectral ranges

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Good practice guide

Use of the prototype sources for the ultraviolet spectral range

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1. Scope

This Good Practice Guide describes the design, specifications, operating conditions, and limitations of the developed sources for the ultraviolet spectral range.

2. Definitions

Dissemination of the (spectral) irradiance: A procedure allowing the comparison of (spectral) irradiance measurements with a measurement standard representing the (spectral) irradiance quantity.

Ultraviolet (UV) radiation: Optical radiation for which the wavelengths are shorter than those for visible radiation. For UV radiation, the range between 100 nm and 400 nm is commonly subdivided into:

UV-A: 315 nm to 400 nm,

UV-B: 280 nm to 315 nm, and

UV-C: 100 nm to 280 nm.

(see 17-21-008 in [CIE S 017:2020]).

According to ISO 20473:2007, ultraviolet (UV) radiation includes the UV-A and UV-B spectral ranges, i.e., 280 nm to 380 nm. The UV-C spectral range is divided into vacuum ultraviolet (VUV; 100 nm to 190 nm) and deep ultraviolet (DUV; 190 nm to 280 nm). Also 1 nm to 100 nm spectral range is defined as extreme ultraviolet (EUV).

Irradiance: Density of incident radiant flux with respect to area at a point on a real or imaginary surface, $E_e = d\Phi_e/dA$, where Φ_e is the radiant flux and A is the area on which the radiant flux is incident. The irradiance is expressed in $W\ m^{-2}$ (see 17-21-053 in [CIE S 017:2020]).

Measurement standard: Realisation of the definition of a given quantity, with stated quantity value and associated measurement uncertainty, used as a reference (see 5.1 in [JCGM 200:2012]).

Primary standard: Measurement standard established using a primary reference measurement procedure, or created as an artefact, chosen by convention (see 5.4 in [JCGM 200:2012]). For (spectral) irradiance primary standards are represented by blackbody radiators, synchrotron radiation or cryogenic radiometers.

Realisation of the (spectral) irradiance quantity: Procedure allowing either (1) producing a well determined (spectral) irradiance, or (2) to determine the (spectral) irradiance on a specific plane. The case (1) is usually based on radiant sources, while the case (2) is based on detectors.

Spectral irradiance: Density of irradiance, $E_e(\lambda)$, with respect to wavelength, λ : $E_{e,\lambda} = dE_e(\lambda)/d\lambda$. The spectral irradiance is expressed in $W\ m^{-2}\ nm^{-1}$ (see 17-21-056 in [CIE S 017:2020]).

Transfer standard: Standard whose quantities are determined by measurements (calibration) traceable to a primary standard, and which allows the relevant quantity to be transferred.

3. Source based on UV LED and UV phosphors

3.1. Design description

The new UV standard source depicted in Figure 1 has been designed for wavelength region from 250 nm to 450 nm. The source consists of a UVC LED matrix emitting radiation at the wavelength of 277 nm, and a UVA + UVB phosphor disk that absorbs a big part of the LED radiation and re-emits it at longer wavelengths covering UV-A and UV-B regions. The LED produces approximately 200 mW of radiation and consumes approximately 17 W of electrical power. The LED matrix is thus attached on an air-cooled heatsink to get rid of the excess heat. A UV coated Ø75 mm plano-convex lens has been added to the design to collect intensity. The focal length of the lens is 90 mm, and it has been set off-focus, to produce a blurred beam profile instead of a focused image to maintain spatial uniformity.

The intensity at the measurement distance of 500 mm is close to a 1 kW incandescent halogen lamp at 500 mm distance as can be seen in Figure 2. Figure 3 presents the key components of the light source, an LED matrix of 3 x 3 LEDs and a phosphor disk, containing UV emitting phosphor forming a layer on top of a quartz disk.

Figure 1: UV light source based on a UV-C LED matrix and a phosphor component covering UV-A and UV-B regions. Visible are the aluminium heat sink stabilising the temperature of the LED and the phosphor component, and the outermost lens condensing radiation.

Figure 2: Spectral irradiance of the new source at the distance of 500 mm (black solid line) and spectral irradiance of a 1 kW incandescent halogen lamp (green dashed line) for comparison. The lowest of the three peaks at the wavelength of 277 nm is produced by the LED matrix. The emission at higher wavelengths including the three peaks at the wavelengths near 310 nm, 340 nm and 375 nm are produced by the phosphor disk.

Figure 3: Components of the UV light source, (a) the LED matrix, and (b) three prototype pieces of the phosphor disk.

3.2. Specifications

Figure 4 presents the optical arrangement of the source built inside an optical tube. Distance between the LED matrix and the phosphor disk is $d_{\text{Phos}} = 22.9$ mm. Distance between the phosphor disk and the lens is $d_{\text{Lens}} = 64.0$ mm. The distance from the lens to the outermost surface of the tube is $d_{\text{Cap}} = 47.3$ mm.

The reference plane for distance measurements is the outermost surface of the tube with its protecting cap closed. Measurement distance from this reference plane is $d_{\text{Meas}} = 500.0$ mm.

Figure 4: Optical arrangement of the source. For dimensions, see text.

The LED matrix is operated with current of 1.000 A. Leads have banana plugs. The voltage across the lamp rises upto 17.3 V.

The fan is operated with a voltage source providing 5 V via banana plugs. Inside the heat sink, there is a 10 k Ω NTC thermistor that is read with a multimeter. There is an adapter providing banana plugs for connection.

The output spectrum is according to Figure 2. The total irradiance in the measurement plane is $\sim 517 \text{ mW m}^{-2}$ integrated over wavelength. The irradiance of the LED peak is 47 mW m^{-2} integrated over the wavelength range from 250 nm to 295 nm. The corresponding irradiance over the phosphor region between 296 nm and 450 nm is 470 mW m^{-2} .

3.3. Safety and handling instructions

The light source produces UV radiation. The amount is not high but may be harmful to eyes if stared at. Use of safety glasses is recommended.

The UV radiation generates tiny amounts of ozone.

3.4. Operating conditions

Environment

The light source has been designed and tested to be used in ordinary laboratory conditions, temperature preferably 23 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Fan cooling

The LED matrix generates about 17 W of power. With the fan on, the temperature of the heat sink and the LED matrix rises to 29 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, 6 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ above the environmental temperature. Without fan (not recommended) the temperature rises to above 35 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The fan is operated with a 5 V power supply.

Electrical parameters

The LED matrix is operated with 1.000 A DC current. Voltage over the lamp is monitored and compared to earlier values. The voltage level is approximately 17.3 V.

Alignment and reference plane

The measuring device should be positioned 500.0 mm from the reference plane (front plate), on an optical axis defined by a mirror placed in contact with the front plate and a laser reflected from the mirror, and the centre of the front plate marked with an X.

Temporal stability

A warm-up time of 1 h should be allowed. The intensity gradually decays. Thus, a record is kept on the lamp burn hours, including voltage across the lamp in the beginning and at the end.

3.5. Limitations

3.5.1. Ageing

The intensity of the lamp decays gradually as can be seen in Figure 5. Intensity integrated over the LED peak region, from 250 nm to 295 nm, drops by 0.11 %/h. Corresponding decay in the phosphor region, integrated from 296 nm to 450 nm is 0.03 %/h.

Figure 5: Ageing of the lamp. Blue circles denote irradiance values integrated over the full spectral range from 250 nm to 450 nm. Orange crosses are irradiance integrated over the LED peak, and green triangles are irradiances integrated over the phosphor region.

3.5.2. Spatial uniformity

Figure 6: Spatial uniformity of the irradiance field measured at the distance of 500 mm. (a) Measurement wavelength 280 nm corresponding to the LED peak, and (b) 334 nm corresponding to the phosphor region.

The lens used to collect radiation causes significant non-uniformity to the irradiance field as can be seen in Figure 6. The non-uniformity is slightly different for the LED peak and the phosphor region of the spectrum, because the sources appear at different locations.

Figure 7 shows a magnified figure over a small region in the centre of the measurement plane. Figure 8 shows correction factors that may be taken into account when comparing measurement devices with varied input aperture sizes.

Figure 7: Magnified figure of the spatial uniformity over a region ± 15 mm in X- and Y-directions. Measurement has been carried out with a 3 mm aperture.

Figure 8: Irradiance masked through different sizes of measurement apertures. Figures have been obtained by integrating the data of Figure 7 over varied circular areas.

3.5.3. Size of source and distance dependence.

The light from the source is condensed with a lens having 75 mm diameter. When measuring, this whole area should be visible and if blocked for dark signal measurement, the whole area should be blocked.

The lens causes the distance behaviour to deviate significantly from inverse square law. Thus, distance corrections and uncertainties cannot be calculated with inverse square law.

4. Source based on UV LEDs

4.1. Design description

The tuneable broadband UV LED source is designed and established having 250 nm to 405 nm wavelength range and higher than 1 mW m⁻² at each wavelength. The source consists of 79 LEDs, arranged in fourteen spectral groups, each group containing LEDs with a different peak wavelength. The model numbers and specifications of the LEDs used in the designed source are provided in Table 1.

Table 1: LED components of the tuneable broadband UV LED source.

	Model No	WL (nm)	LED Quantity	Optical PWR (mW)	Technology	O/P Optics
UVC	HYE35P40F250AG-P1	255	5	90	AlGaIn	Flat quartz glass
UVC	HYE35P30F260AG-P1	265	6	60	AlGaIn	Flat quartz glass
UVC	HYE35P20F270AG-P1	275	11	35	AlGaIn	Flat quartz glass
UVB	XBT-3535-285 nm	285	6	70	AlGaIn	Borosilicate glass
UVB	HYE35P20F290AG-P1	295	5	70	AlGaIn	Flat quartz glass
UVB	HYE35P20F310AG-P1	310	13	30	AlGaIn	Flat quartz glass
UVA	HYE35P20F325AG-P1	325	13	90	AlGaIn	Flat quartz glass
UVA	HYE35P20F340AG-P1	340	11	40	AlGaIn	Flat quartz glass
UVA	LN-SMD3838UVB-P3	350	4	100	AlGaIn	Quartz glass
UVA	GT-3535P365-1CC0-GH45M	365	1	1200	AlInGaIn	120 degree silicone lens
UVA	RZX-S3838-375NM-3W-N60	375	1	1000	AlGaIn	Quartz lens
UVA	GT-3535P380-1CC0-GH45M	385	1	1200	AlInGaIn	120 degree silicone lens
UVA	GT-3535P395-1CC0-GH45M	395	1	1200	AlInGaIn	120 degree silicone lens
UVA	GT-3535P400-1CC0-GH45M	405	1	1000	AlInGaIn	120 degree silicone lens

The LEDs were positioned on a circular PCB in the configuration shown in Figure 9 and Figure 10 in order to achieve uniform irradiation.

Figure 9: Schematic layout of the 79 UV LEDs, illustrating the placement and wavelength classification of the LEDs within the circular PCB.

Figure 10: Picture of the LEDs on the PCB.

Multi-channel current driver provides current the 14 LED groups. Each current channel can be set a current value responding to relating LED group. The current values can be set the maximum or less any other current

value of the relating LED. The multi-channel current driver can give options to drive one or multi LEDs / LED groups to have one or several wavelength configurations at optic output while aimed broadband UV LED source. It gives flexible usage and opportunity having different spectral power distributions. The multi-channel current driver is powered by an external DC power supply. The current control is performed by “UV LED PROGRAM V1.065” software whose user interface is depicted in Figure 11.

Figure 11: The source control software interface.

For temperature stability of the LEDs, the LED PCB is mounted on a Thermoelectric Cooler (TEC) (Arroyo Instruments 286-C0866 TECMount) which was custom-manufactured based on the LED PCB size and the expected thermal load.

4.2. Specifications

The dimensional drawings of the customised cold plate of the TEC are shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: (a) Drawing of the cold plate of the TEC (lengths in mm). (b) Photo of the LED PCB on TEC.

The spectrum given in Figure 13 shows multiple low-intensity peaks in the region from 260 nm to 350 nm, representing the combined emission of several UV LED groups with closely spaced wavelengths. The two strong maxima around ~365 nm and ~395 nm indicate that the LED types at these wavelengths contribute the dominant radiant power. The low-intensity peaks between 260 nm and 350 nm, where the smallest peaks are below approximately $0.03 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ nm}^{-1}$. The two dominant emission bands occur near ~365 nm and ~395 nm, with the maximum peak reaching about $0.27 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ nm}^{-1}$.

Figure 13: (a) Spectral irradiance of the source at a distance of 500 mm. (b) Output of the source.

The source exhibits very stable spectral output over the UV range after the initial warm-up period. In the region from 250 nm to 300 nm, the stability after 30 minutes remains within $\pm 1 \%$, while in the 300–405 nm range the variation is further reduced to below $\pm 0.5 \%$ is shown in Figure 14. After one hour of operation, the stability curve shows an additional improvement, indicating that the system reaches a steady thermal and electrical equilibrium.

Figure 14: Stability of the source.

4.3. Safety and handling instructions

- Do not move when the source is switched on.
- Apply the current to the LEDs after TEC is active.
- Never look directly at the emitting surface while the source is operating.
- Always wear appropriate UV-blocking protective eyewear and laboratory gloves.
- Avoid exposing skin directly to the UV beam. Use shielding whenever possible.
- Do not block airflow around measurement area.
- Keep the device away from water, solvents, and corrosive chemicals.

4.4. Operating conditions

Environment

Conditions with ambient temperature between 20 °C and 30 °C and relative humidity between 30 % and 70 % are recommended.

Thermoelectric cooling

Since the large number of LEDs generates a significant thermal load on the 10 cm-diameter PCB, temperature monitoring is performed not only via the temperature sensor located behind the TEC cold plate but also by an additional sensor placed at the centre of the PCB. Because the target temperature on the PCB is 25 °C, the LED board can be maintained at this level when the TEC is fixed at 18 °C. To ensure stable source irradiance, the TEC temperature must remain constant at 18 °C so that the PCB temperature, as monitored by the onboard sensor, stays close to 25 °C.

Electrical parameters

The source must be switched on only when the TEC is active. The external DC power supply must provide 12 V and 15 A to drive the multi-channel current driver. Using the user interface software, the operator must set the driving current for the LEDs across 14 channels, ensuring that the current for each channel remains below the maximum value indicated as “MAX:” in the interface.

Alignment and reference plane

The sensor should be positioned such that its centre aligns with the centre of the PCB. A distance of 500 mm is recommended for the measurements.

Spatial homogeneity

The physical configuration, where multiple LEDs of various wavelengths are positioned within a 10 cm circular PCB results in a broad area of emission. Consequently, the spatial homogeneity cannot be expected to be as ideal as that of a point source. Nevertheless, measurements have not been conducted to characterise this parameter.

Temporal stability

A warm-up time of 1 h should be allowed.

4.5. Limitations

The main limitations of the source in comparison with a standard QTH lamp are

- Irradiance spatial homogeneity
- Spectral lateral homogeneity

Acknowledgments

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Good practice guide

Use of the transfer standard light sources developed for the
VIS spectral range

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1. Scope

This Good Practice Guide describes the design, specifications, operating conditions, and limitations of the developed sources for the visible spectral range between 360 nm and 830 nm.

2. Definitions

Dissemination of the unit of the (spectral) irradiance: A procedure allowing the comparison of (spectral) irradiance measurements with a measurement standard representing the unit of the (spectral) irradiance quantity.

Irradiance: Density of incident radiant flux, Φ_e , with respect to area, A , at a point on a real or imaginary surface, $E_e = d\Phi_e/dA$. The irradiance is expressed in $W\ m^{-2}$ (see 17-21-053 in [CIE S 017:2020]).

Measurement standard: Realization of the definition of a given quantity, with stated quantity value and associated measurement uncertainty, used as a reference (see 5.1 in [JCGM 200:2012]).

Primary standard: Measurement standard established using a primary reference measurement procedure, or created as an artefact, chosen by convention (see 5.4 in [JCGM 200:2012]). For (spectral) irradiance primary standards are represented by blackbody radiators, synchrotron radiation or cryogenic radiometers.

Realization of the unit of the (spectral) irradiance: Procedure allowing either (1) producing a well determined (spectral) irradiance, or (2) to determine the (spectral) irradiance on a specific plane. The case (1) is usually based on radiant sources, while the case (2) is based on detectors.

Spectral irradiance: Density of the irradiance, $E_e(\lambda)$ with respect to wavelength, λ , $E_{e,\lambda} = dE_e(\lambda)/d\lambda$. The spectral irradiance is expressed in $W\ m^{-2}\ nm^{-1}$ (see 17-21-056 in [CIE S 017:2020]).

Transfer standard: Standard whose quantities are determined by measurements (calibration) traceable to a primary standard, and which allows the relevant quantity to be transferred.

Visible (VIS) radiation: optical radiation capable of causing a visual sensation directly.

There are no precise limits for the spectral range of visible radiation since they depend upon the amount of radiant flux reaching the retina and the responsivity of the observer. The lower limit is generally taken between 360 nm and 400 nm and the upper limit between 760 nm and 830 nm. (see 17-21-003 in [CIE S 017:2020]).

In this document we define the lower VIS limit to 360 nm and the upper VIS limit to 830 nm to cover any existing wavelength range definitions.

3. General requirements and preliminary considerations

3.1. Spectral distribution of the transfer standard

The uncertainty contributions arising from the spectrometer's wavelength scale uncertainty become particularly significant when steep spectral slopes are present, such as at the edges of LED emission peaks. In these regions, even a small wavelength error or wavelength uncertainty cause a disproportionately large change in the measured spectral irradiance, thereby dominating the total measurement uncertainty. To minimize this effect, it is advisable to design or select light sources whose spectral distributions avoid sharp transitions or peak structures whenever possible. A smoother spectrum reduces the effect of wavelength calibration errors and improves the reliability and reproducibility of the measurement results.

Figure 1 – RGB LED: It is clearly recognisable that a small shift in the wavelength leads to a considerable change in the spectral irradiance at the edges of the LED peaks.

Taking the measurement uncertainty into account, the ideal spectrum is therefore one in which the spectral irradiance is constant over the entire visible wavelength range. This distribution is called CIE illuminant E. CIE illuminant E is a purely hypothetical, idealised light source that has equal energy at each wavelength in the visible spectrum. It does not correspond to any natural or common artificial light, but is used as a mathematical and conceptual reference in colorimetry.

Figure 2 – Illuminant E. It is not a blackbody and therefore does not have a true colour temperature, but its chromaticity can be approximated by a daylight-type illuminant with a correlated colour temperature of about 5455 K.

Illuminant E is a hypothetical, non-existent spectrum that cannot be perfectly realised in practice. Therefore, calibrated light sources with this spectrum are not available. The spectrum of the new reference light source should nevertheless be adapted as closely as possible to the CIE E distribution.

3.2. Selection of LEDs – Approach A

A total of 35 different LED types from various manufacturers were identified as suitable based on a market survey and subsequently purchased. In total, 120 LEDs were operated on a temperature-stabilized heatsink on the surface of a 1.65-meter integrating sphere equipped with a spectrometer for approximately 1000 hours.

This experimental setup enables consistent measurement conditions and long-term performance testing of the LEDs, ensuring stable temperature and precise spectral characterization throughout the duration of the test.

Figure 3 shows the rear of the active temperature-controlled LED board mounted on the side port of an integrating sphere. There are 120 relays for selectively switching on and off single or multiple LEDs.

Figure 3 – Temperature controlled LED-Board

Figure 4 shows an overview of the integrating sphere used during the first operating test of the LEDs.

- **Figure 4 – Image of the opened integrating sphere during the first operational test. The lamp holder rod was of course removed during the seasoning tests.**

The LEDs are operated simultaneously for seasoning. Spectral measurements were taken regularly during the seasoning process. In addition, the LEDs are operated and measured individually from time to time. This was done approximately every 100 hours.

Figure 5 – Close-up of the 120 LEDs on the inside of the sphere

In the end, 28 LED types were identified as suitable based on their long-term aging behavior, meaning they showed stable output and only limited degradation over the test period. Each of these LEDs was then characterized individually to obtain its precise spectral power distribution. Using these measured spectra, a composite spectrum was numerically simulated by combining the contributions of the selected LEDs so that the resulting distribution covers the entire visible range and is as close as possible to an equal-energy (near flat) spectrum. This synthesized spectrum can serve as a tailored broadband illuminant for applications that require uniform spectral coverage, such as spectroradiometer calibration.

Figure 6 – Simulated spectrum (rainbow-coloured) from the combination of the measured individual spectra of the LEDs (white spectra).

There are still individual peaks, but with a maximum variation of $\pm 20\%$, which seems acceptable. The individual LED types and the associated operating currents for achieving an energy spectrum are listed below.

Table 1 – Overview of LEDs that have proven to be suitable after seasoning and characterisation.

Number	Peak Wavelength or CCT	LED Type	Current /A	Relative Current
1	365nm	SMB1N-365V	0.361	100%
2	4000K	SCP9TTF1HEL1TUH34E	0.341	95%
3	770nm	SMB1N-770	0.309	86%
4	727nm	GF CSSPM1.24-2T4T-1	0.277	77%

5	850nm	SFH 4716AS	0.273	76%
6	405nm	15335340AA350	0.272	75%
7	800nm	SMB1N-800D	0.265	73%
8	470nm	GB QSSPA1.13-HYJX-35-1	0.221	61%
9	385nm	SMB1N-385V	0.220	61%
10	430nm	SMB1N-430H	0.217	60%
11	395nm	SMB1N-395V	0.212	59%
12	830nm	SMB1N-830N	0.198	55%
13	700nm	SMB1N-700D	0.192	53%
14	375nm	SMB1N-375V	0.139	39%
15	750nm	SMB1N-750D	0.128	36%
16	490nm	SMB1N-490H	0.113	31%
17	680nm	SMB1N-680D	0.107	30%
18	515nm	SMB1N-515V	0.060	17%
19	657nm	GH CSSRM4.24-V7V9-1-1-700-R33	0.048	13%
20	830nm	SMB1N-830N	0.040	11%
21	448nm	GD CSSRML.14-U9V2-24-1-350-R33	0.038	11%
22	550nm	SMB1N-550H	0.027	7%
23	593nm	GY CSHPM1.23-KPKR-36	0.025	7%
24	568nm	LXML-PX02-0000	0.019	5%
25	385nm	SMB1N-385V	0.009	2%
26	528nm	GT QSSPA1.13-LSLU-26-1	0.003	1%
27	570nm	SMC570	0.003	1%
28	505nm	LV CRBP.01-KXLY-AD-Q525-350-R18	0.002	0.5%

To achieve an approximately equal-energy spectrum, the drive currents of the individual LEDs had to be adjusted over a very wide range, which made the system inherently complex and sensitive. Attempts to balance the optical output by arranging LEDs in parallel groups and using series resistors to trim the flux of each device were only partially successful. Even small changes in the temperature led to noticeable shifts in the relative output of the individual LEDs, because their forward voltage and efficiency are strongly temperature dependent.

Grouping several LEDs and operating them in series reduced the number of channels somewhat, but even in this configuration at least ten independent current drivers were still required. Such a large number of separate, precisely controlled current supplies is not useful for a transfer standard light source, as it increases cost, complexity, and the risk of drift or mismatch between channels. In practice, this architecture would require continuous monitoring and frequent recalibration to maintain the expected uncertainties of the target spectrum, which contradicts the goal of a simple, robust, and reproducible reference source.

Fortunately, a new type of LED came onto the market during the characterisation process that proved to be more suitable. This approach was therefore discontinued at this point and the other LED type is described in the following chapter.

3.3. Selection of LEDs – Approach B

Due to the previously described issue of needing at least ten separate current drivers, another market survey for alternative LEDs was conducted. In this search, a new product line from Yujileds was identified that appeared particularly promising. These LEDs combine several pump LEDs with different wavelength-converting phosphors in a single package to generate a broadband spectral power distribution. The manufacturer even advertises a spectrum that closely resembles the hypothetical CIE illuminant E, i.e., with a very smooth, nearly equal-energy distribution across the visible range.

Figure 7 – Screenshot of Yujileds advertisement

Such integrated broadband LEDs are attractive for calibration purposes because they can provide wide spectral coverage with only one or a few current channels instead of many individually driven monochromatic LEDs. This significantly reduces system complexity, wiring effort, and the risk of spectral instability due to mismatched or drifting current sources, making the realization of a practical calibration light source much more feasible.

According to the data sheet, a single LED provides an optical output of approximately 3.6 W when driven at 18 V and 200 mA. To achieve a sufficiently high irradiance at a distance of about 700 mm on the entrance optics of a spectroradiometer, ten of these LEDs are driven in series. In this configuration, the same current flows through all the devices, so the total optical power is approximately the sum of the individual contributions, while the required supply voltage increases accordingly. Operating multiple LEDs in series on a thermally stabilised heatsink helps to maintain uniform operating conditions and reduces current balancing problems, which is important for achieving stable and reproducible irradiance at the measurement plane of the spectroradiometer being calibrated.

Figure 8 shows an overview measurement of 10 LEDs in a distance of 700mm

Figure 8 – PTB Measurement of 10 Yujiled LEDs @ 700mm Distance

As can be seen in Figure 8, the spectral irradiance above 400nm is sufficiently high and also quite constant over the wavelength range. In particular, the phosphor-converted part of the emission spectrum shows almost no narrowband peaks, indicating a homogeneous and broadband output in the visible. However,

below 400nm the irradiance is too low to be useful for the requested calibration or measurement applications. Fortunately, suitable LEDs were available from the earlier Approach A to fill these short wavelength gaps. By carefully combining the phosphor-converted broadband LEDs with these additional UV or violet LEDs, it was possible to achieve a more continuous and sufficiently intense spectrum through the entire visible range. This hybrid approach exploits the smoothness and stability of the phosphor-converted LEDs in the visible range, while supplementing the spectrum where their output is weak, enabling the construction of a calibration source that closely meets the requirements for uniform spectral coverage and high total irradiance.

Figure 9 – Combination of 5 UV-LEDs and 10 Yujiled LEDs @ 700mm

Figure 9 shows the combined spectrum of the ten Yujiled LEDs together with additional UV LEDs with peak wavelengths between 365 and 405 nm. In this configuration, the basic requirements for a continuous visible spectrum with sufficiently high irradiance are met, and the overall spectral power distribution appears smooth and free of pronounced narrowband artefacts over most of the VIS range.

Prior to further optimisation or fine tuning of the spectral shape, emphasis was placed on evaluating the temporal stability of this LED combination over operating time. For use as a calibration light source, not only the instantaneous spectral distribution but also its long-term stability is critical. Systematic seasoning tests were therefore planned to quantify how both total radiant flux and spectral shape evolve during prolonged operation, and to verify that any changes remain within acceptable tolerance limits for high precision spectroradiometer calibration.

3.4. Seasoning

LEDs should be seasoned (pre-aged) before being used as reference lamps because their aging process affects performance stability over time. Initially, LEDs experience more significant changes in radiant flux, color characteristics, and efficiency due to various degradation mechanisms including phosphor conversion efficiency decline and thermal effects. With increasing operating time, the rate of aging slows down, leading to a more stable output, which is crucial when LEDs are used as calibration or reference light sources. Seasoning helps to ensure that the LED's output has settled into a stable phase where temporal changes are minimal, improving measurement reliability and reducing uncertainty caused by ongoing aging effects during use. This time-dependent behavior means the LED's light output and spectral properties are more consistent after initial aging, making it better suited as a reference

Figure 10 – relative change of irradiance (not spectral irradiance) over 294 hours

Figure 10 shows the change in irradiance over the full range of wavelengths emitted by the LED source over time. After an initial run-in period of about 150 hours, the signal follows a very well linear decrease that can be described mathematically with high accuracy. The observed drift is significantly less than 10^{-5} per hour, so the irradiance remains after mathematical correction effectively constant for most practical measurement times.

Such a small, predictable aging rate is highly advantageous for establishing a transfer standard, as the temporal behaviour can be reliably modelled and, if necessary, corrected in the calibration procedure. This means that calibration laboratories can use the source to transfer spectral irradiance scales between instruments or facilities while maintaining traceability and quantifiable uncertainty contributions from source ageing.

Figure 11 – Seasoning behaviour over 294 hours. A spectrum was measured every 2 hours.

Figure 11 shows the spectrally resolved seasoning behaviour of the LED source over a total operating time of 294 hours. For this experiment, one spectrum was recorded every two hours, and all 147 spectra were plotted on top of each other to visualize how the spectral irradiance evolves over time across the full wavelength range.

In the subsequent plot, the relative change of each spectrum with respect to the final measurement is shown. The blue curve corresponds to the first recorded spectrum and indicates that the signal around 500 nm was roughly 4% higher compared to the end of the test. Toward longer operating times, the individual curves lie increasingly close together, clearly illustrating that the rate of change diminishes with time and the system gradually approaches a quasi-steady state, which is advantageous for establishing a stable calibration source.

Rel. changes of the Spectral Irradiance @ 700mm /W/nm/m²

Figure 12 – Spectral changes over 294 hours. A spectrum was measured every 2 hours. The diagram shows the relative changes compared to the last measured spectrum.

Figure 13 shows only the last 20 measurements taken over the last 40 hours of operation. Over most of the wavelength range, the relative changes in spectral irradiance are negligible, indicating that the source has largely reached a steady state.

Rel. changes of the Spectral Irradiance @ 700mm /W/nm/m²

Figure 13 – Spectral changes over 40 hours. A spectrum was measured every 2 hours. The diagram shows the relative changes compared to the last measured spectrum

As expected, the largest variations occur at the 365 nm UV LEDs with the highest photon energy, and there is a distinct residual peak around 500 nm where small drift is still visible. Nevertheless, the corresponding rates of change per hour—below about $5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ h}^{-1}$ at 495 nm and $1.3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ h}^{-1}$ at 360 nm—remain well within an acceptable range for high-precision applications. Overall, this behavior demonstrates that the LED combination is sufficiently stable to serve as the basis for a spectral irradiance transfer standard.

3.5. Short term instability of the transfer standard

The activity report A1.2.2 investigates experimentally how short-term instabilities in LED light sources, used as transfer standards, influence the calibration of spectroradiometers concerning irradiance measurements. It specifically analyzes how integration time, periodic fluctuations in irradiance, and the spectroradiometer's own noise impact measurement accuracy. The methodology involved modulating an LED-based light source with a controllable power supply to produce periodic irradiance variations at different amplitudes and periods.

A photodiode monitored these variations every 0.1 seconds, while the actual measurements were performed with a spectroradiometer, which used various integration times, simulated by adjusting distance.

The results showed that irradiance variations caused by modulation could be kept below 0.01%, with the spectroradiometer noise dominating measurement errors when fluctuations stayed under this threshold. Longer integration times and lower modulation frequencies increased the signal-to-noise ratio, and a high correlation was observed across different wavelengths, indicating that the dominant noise affected all spectral regions similarly. Spectral integration did not reduce this noise further. Theoretical analysis supported that the relative standard deviation of the spectral response depended on the ratio between the integration time and the modulation period.

The key conclusion was that short-term fluctuations in the light source below 0.01% do not significantly distort calibration results. Instead, the primary influence comes from the spectroradiometer's own noise and the precision of the integration time measurement. These findings are particularly relevant for laboratories employing LED-based transfer standards, providing guidance for selecting optimal measurement parameters and understanding the limits of light source stability's effect on measurement accuracy.

Since the fluctuations in the irradiance of an LED light source are strongly correlated with the fluctuations of its power supply current, the noise in the current source can be considered a proportional factor influencing the noise of the light source. In other words, variations in the electrical current directly translate to proportional variations in the light output, meaning that any instability or noise in the driving current inherently causes corresponding fluctuations in the LED's emitted light intensity.

Therefore, it is most important to ensure that the power supply feeding the LED has a high level of stability, ideally better than 0.01%, to minimize noise and fluctuations in light output. Maintaining such strict current stability is essential to achieve accurate and reliable measurements, as even small current deviations can significantly affect the LED's emitted light intensity. This emphasizes the need to use high-quality, stable current sources or LED drivers in precision applications.

The Keithley 2460 SourceMeter has a current stability specification that typically is better than 0.1% under normal conditions. Specifically, for the 200 mA range, it offers very precise current sourcing with stability and accuracy including line and load regulation on the order of 0.01% of range plus very small incremental errors. This means the current supplied at 200 mA is stable with fluctuations well below 0.1%, and often close to or under 0.01% depending on the specific measurement setup and conditions. This makes the Keithley 2460 highly suitable for operating the transfer standard for precision calibrations.

The entire report can be found in Appendix A1.

3.6. Temperature stabilisation

LEDs should be operated on a temperature-stabilized heatsink when used as references because temperature significantly impacts their optical parameters.

The emitted flux and spectral characteristics of LEDs vary with temperature, typically decreasing optical power as temperature rises due to mechanisms such as non-radiative recombination and carrier leakage.

Stabilizing the temperature ensures more consistent light output and colour stability, which is crucial for reliable measurements and calibration. Without temperature control, variations of ambient temperature affect the thermal equilibrium and lead to fluctuations in light output and peak wavelengths, reducing the stability and accuracy of the LED as a reference source.

Using a temperature-stabilized heatsink minimizes these temperature-induced variations, enhancing the precision and repeatability of optical referencing with LEDs. The used Sourcemeters and the temperature stabilisation should be connected to the mains for at least 2 hours. The LEDs of the LIS-A² light source can then be switched on and measurements can be taken after a warm-up time of around 5 minutes.

Figure 14 – This is a separate enclosure designed to interface with the LIS-A² light source. On the front panel, there are connectors for powering three independent LED circuits, each labeled with its respective current and voltage ratings. A toggle switch activates the built-in alignment laser. A green indicator LED in the right image shows that the source has reached thermal equilibrium.

3.7. Design description

The design of the LIS-A light source from the EURAMET European Metrology Programme for Innovation and Research (EMPIR) project 15SIB07 PhotoLED (<http://photoled.aalto.fi/>) was successful and serves as the basis for the development of a broadband VIS source.

Figure 15 – LIS-A reference light source

The housing includes high-quality temperature stabilisation and a proven and good arrangement of individual LEDs. As the new source requires several different LED types to be operated at different currents, the housing and circuit design have been adapted. In addition, a laser was built into the housing to align the source, which shines through the LED board and specifies the direction in which the coupling optics of the spectroradiometer should be attached.

The result is a source which we call LIS-A² and which is shown and described in the following images.

Figure 16 – The left rendered image shows the LIS-A² source. The marked laser beam indicates the measurement direction. The right image shows the real prototype during the NEWSTAND measurement campaign at the PTB.

Figure 17 – Front view of the LIS-A² with dimensions in millimetres.

Figure 18 – Side view of the LIS-A² with dimensions in millimetres.

Figure 19 – Bottom side view. An optical post or tripod can be attached to the bottom of the LIS-A² standard light source. There is one M6 tapped hole and one 1/4" tapped hole at the base. There are two additional bores with H7 tolerance. The bottom side should be aligned perpendicular to gravity.

3.8. Transfer standard light source: LIS-A²

For the measurement campaign at PTB and for comparison measurements between different laboratories, three LIS-A² standard lamps were built.

Figure 20 – Three LIS-A² artifacts with and without protective caps

The images in Figure 20 show three LIS-A² standard lamps arranged vertically. In the left panel, each lamp is fitted with a protective cap covering the emission aperture to shield the front glass and LED array and prevent contamination or mechanical damage during storage and transport. In the right panel, these caps have been removed, revealing the circular LED boards with the ring of broadband Yujileds and the central UV LEDs inside each housing. The consistent mechanical design and interchangeable front caps support reproducible positioning and handling in calibration setups, while the robust enclosures provide thermal and mechanical stability for the light sources.

Figure 21 – LED arrangement and central LASER beam for alignment

Each lamp contains an LED board with ten Yujiled CIE-E LEDs arranged in a circular ring and an additional set of five UV LEDs with peak wavelengths of 365 nm, 375 nm, 385 nm, 395 nm, and 405 nm mounted inside the ring.

Figure 22 – Full LIS-A² setup

Figure 22 shows a single standard LIS-A² lamp and its associated power sources. The LIS-A² is mounted on an adjustable post on the optical table, while three stacked SourceMeter units on the right provide precisely controlled currents for the different LED strings. The LED drive currents are set to very low levels to avoid saturating the camera image, so that the individual emitters are clearly visible. The inner ring of the LED array shows the different coloured UV LEDs, surrounded by the brighter broadband Yujileds which form the outer ring and dominate the visible output.

Every board is divided into three independent current circuits. Since connecting all ten broadband LEDs in series would require an impractically high supply voltage of about 180 V, they are split into two separate strings of five identical LEDs, each operated at 200 mA. A third circuit supplies the five UV LEDs. The drive current of the UV channel is adjusted so that, in combination with the broadband Yujileds, the resulting composite spectrum exhibits an almost constant spectral irradiance over the entire visible range as shown in Figure 23. This electrical architecture allows precise, reproducible control of the spectral power distribution while keeping the operating voltages within a safe and convenient range.

Figure 23 – Relative spectral irradiance of a LIS-A² artifact

Because the UV LEDs inside the LIS-A could not be arranged in a perfectly rotationally symmetric pattern, the irradiance uniformity had to be verified at different distances from the source. The following figures show the relative spectral irradiance over the wavelength range from 340 nm to 800 nm for two distances. The blue circle marks a field with a diameter of 11.3 mm, corresponding to the typical entrance optics of spectroradiometers according to CIE report 127:2007 (Measurement of LEDs), while the black circle indicates a 20 mm diameter, which covers the vast majority of practical detector apertures. Since typical measurement distances lie between 350 mm and 700 mm, the irradiance distribution was characterized for both distances. In both cases, the color maps demonstrate that within the blue and black circles the relative deviations from the central irradiance level are very small, indicating a highly uniform illumination of the detector aperture. For intermediate distances, which will be used in real measurement setups, the field can be expected to be at least as uniform, so the LIS-A² geometry is well suited for accurate spectroradiometer calibration without introducing significant spatial nonuniformity errors.

Figure 24 – VIS irradiance uniformity at a distance of 350 mm

Figure 25 – VIS irradiance uniformity at a distance of 700 mm

3.9. Safety and handling instructions

To prevent the source from damage, the following handling instructions must be respected:

- **Avoid looking directly into the illuminated aperture, especially at close distances, as the intense visible and UV radiation may cause eye strain or damage!**
- Use appropriate eye protection when working near the lamp without beam enclosures.
- Ensure that all personnel working with the LIS-A² are trained in its operation and familiar with general LED and UV safety guidelines, including applicable photobiological safety standards.
- The source is meant for operation in laboratory conditions and should not be used in other environments.
- Operate the LIS-A² lamp only with the specified power supplies and wiring; do not modify the electrical connections or exceed the rated currents and voltages.
- Ensure that the protective front cap is mounted whenever the lamp is not in use or is being transported, to prevent mechanical damage and contamination of the optics.
- Allow sufficient ventilation around the housing and do not cover cooling openings; operate the lamp only within the specified ambient temperature range between +10°C and 30°C.
- Switch off the lamp and disconnect it from the power supplies before moving, performing any mechanical adjustments, cleaning, or reconfiguration of the setup.
- Current to the LEDs must not be applied when the TEC is inactive.
- No reverse bias should be applied to the LEDs.
- The source must not be exposed to liquids, moisture, dust or flames. Use only dry, lint-free materials and suitable cleaning agents for the front window; never use aggressive solvents on optical or plastic parts.

The following procedure is recommended to operate the LIS-A² standard light source.

1. Use an M6 or 1/4" optical post to hold the LIS-A² standard light source and align the bottom perpendicular to gravity.
2. Connect all cables, and plug the TEC and Sourcemeters to the mains and switch them on. **Do not activate the power output of the sourcemeters, yet.**
3. Remove the dust protection cap.
4. Align the LIS-A² standard light source. You can use cameras, the internal laser or other devices to do this.
5. Wait at least 2 hours to allow the instruments to warm so that their internal temperature reaches equilibrium. Do not operate the LEDs during this warm-up period. After the warm-up time, the SourceMeters can be assumed to meet their specified accuracy and stability, and you may then enable the outputs and start driving the LEDs.
6. Wait at least until the status LED on the separate enclosure switches on (Figure 14). We recommend waiting for 10 minutes warm-up time to achieve a highly stable thermal equilibrium.
7. Carry out your measurements.
8. Turn off the LEDs.
9. Put the dust protection cap on the LIS-A² standard light source.

3.10. Advantages and disadvantages

In comparison to a quartz halogen lamp, the main drawback of the LIS-A² LED source is the presence of individual peaks in the spectral distribution rather than a perfectly smooth continuum. In addition, the system requires a temperature controller and several separate current drivers, which increases complexity and cost.

However, during operation the temporal aging of the LEDs is significantly smaller than that of a halogen lamp, so the output remains more stable over long measurement campaigns. The source also exhibits lower intensity noise, and the spectral irradiance between 400 nm and 800 nm is nearly constant, which is advantageous for spectroradiometric calibration.

The most important advantage is the absence of out-of-range stray light. A halogen lamp emits a very large fraction of its power in the infrared, and this strong IR component can generate considerable internal stray light in the blue region of VIS spectroradiometers, thereby degrading measurement accuracy. In contrast, the LIS-A² spectrum is much more similar to common practical light sources used in applications, with minimal emission outside the relevant spectral range, so this reduction in stray light and improved representativeness of real-world illumination conditions is the dominant benefit (substitution method).

22IEM05 NEWSTAND

Activity report

Version Date: 22 May 2024

Task 1.2 Development of broadband transfer standard light sources

A1.2.2 (Partial activity by CSIC in collaboration with PTB) Evaluation of the impact of the light source short-term instability on the calibration in irradiance of spectroradiometer.

Start date: 01 December 2023

Duration: 17 months

Involved partners:
PTB, CSIC, GOO, NPL

1. Introduction

The objective of this work, carried out at the *Instituto de Óptica* in CSIC, is to evaluate the impact of the short-term instability of the light sources developed as transfer standard in the result of the calibration in irradiance of spectroradiometers. This impact depends on the integration time of specific measurements, and on the own read out noise of the test spectroradiometer. We evaluated this experimentally by producing periodic variations of the irradiance on the spectroradiometer with different amplitudes, for different integration times. This periodic variation of the irradiance was produced by controlling the current of the light source.

2. Methodology

CSIC received a LED-based light source (LIS-A) from PTB, whose design is the proposed for the transfer light source in the visible, and a programmable sourcemeter (Model 2460 High-Current Interactive SourceMeter Instrument, Keithley).

The sourcemeter was PC-controlled by Matlab, in order to change dynamically the supply current to LIS-A.

The supply current was limited to a maximum of $I_{\max} = 65$ mA (limit of voltage of 71.3 V), and modified according to the expression:

$$I = I_{\max} \frac{[1 - A \cos(2\pi t/P)]}{(1 + A)} \quad (1)$$

Where t is the time, P the period of variation, and A is an amplitude that allows the relative standard deviation of the irradiance (σ_r) to be modified by selecting $A = 3\sigma_r/2$, as tested experimentally.

In order to monitor the irradiance value, a Hamamatsu Si photodiode (together with a Keithley 6485 picoammeter) was used in front of LIS-A to acquire a value for each change in the supply current. The current is changed every 0.1 s using Eq. (1), and after that the photodiode acquires a value of the photocurrent. When the acquisition is finished a new value of the supply current is set, based on the internal clock of the computer.

Periods, P , of 0 s, 1 s, 2 s, 4 s and 8 s and relative standard deviations, σ_r , of 0.01, 0.001 and 0.0001 were selected for this study. Periods lower than 1 s did not allow a proper sampling on the irradiance variation (it was limited by the monitoring process), whereas we did not see much difference between result with $\sigma_r = 0.0001$ and lower values for this parameter.

Once the correct realization of the periodic variation was verified, the variation of the signal of a spectroradiometer Konica Minolta CS-1000 was tested under the mentioned (P , σ_r) configurations of irradiance. The monitoring of the irradiance with the photodiode was used during this evaluation, by displacing the photodiode to avoid the occlusion of LIS-A from the spectroradiometer. The spectroradiometer was controlled in a parallel session so that it not interferes with the realization of the irradiance modulation. The spectroradiometer takes some time in acquiring a single spectrum (no less than 15 s), because it evaluates first the proper integration time for each level of irradiance. 30 acquisitions were used to evaluate the impact of the short-term instability of the light source (between 8 min and 11 min). In order to evaluate the response at different integration times, we modified the irradiance on the spectroradiometer by modifying the distance. Three distances were selected allowing integration times, t_{int} , of 1.5 s, 3 s and 5.6 s.

A picture of the setup is shown in Figure 26.

Figure 26: Picture of the setup.

3. Results

The results of the relative variation of the irradiance produced by LIS-A under the different (P, σ_r) configurations is shown Figure 27. In addition, in the figure is included the period of 5 s, to show the effect of undersampling the variation of irradiance, and $\sigma_r = 0.00005$, showing that it is possible to achieve such small variation with this method.

Figure 27: Variation of the irradiance produced by LIS-A under the different (P , σ_r) configurations.

In Figure 28, it is shown the relative variation of the irradiance with respect to the supply current. The coefficient of sensitivity is 14.7 A^{-1} , calculated as the slope of the data represented in the figure.

Figure 28: Relative variation of the irradiance with respect to the supply current.

An example of the relative variation of the response of the spectroradiometer is shown in Figure 29, for an integration time of 1.5 s, under the different (P , σ_r) configurations. Note the effect of undersampling in the variation of the response of the spectroradiometer, which makes that the observed period is longer than the period of the irradiance. A wavelength of 580 nm was selected for the results presented in Figure 29, in the fluorescent emission. The analogue figure for the wavelength at 450 nm (blue peak of the emission) is shown in Figure 30. No important differences between both figures are observed. The same plots are represented for spectrally integrated data between 470 nm and 700 nm, and shown in Figure 31.

Figure 29: [Data for 580 nm] Example of the relative variation of the response of the spectroradiometer for an integration time of 1.5 s, under the different (P, σ_r) configurations.

Figure 30: [Data for 450 nm] Example of the relative variation of the response of the spectroradiometer for an integration time of 1.5 s, under the different (P , σ_r) configurations.

Figure 31: [Spectrally integrated data between 470 nm and 700 nm] Example of the relative variation of the response of the spectroradiometer for an integration time of 1.5 s, under the different (P , σ_r) configurations.

The summary of the results is provided in Table 2, where the relative standard deviation of the irradiance (from photodiode) and of the spectroradiometer response (for 580 nm and the spectrally integrated value between 470 nm and 700 nm) are presented for the different configurations and integration times. The results for 580 nm are shown as a plot in Figure 32, where the relative standard deviation of the responses is represented as a function of the ratio between the period of the irradiance and the integration time used by the spectroradiometer. The relevance of expressing this variation according to this independent variable is supported by the theoretical development explained in the “Discussion and conclusions” section, in Eq. (8).

In order to identify any difference among wavelengths, the relative standard deviation of the response of the spectroradiometer, for no modulated irradiance, is shown in Figure 33. The variation in the relative standard deviations at different wavelength is mostly due the different magnitude of irradiance (the relative standard deviation due exclusively to the photon noise decreases inversely proportional the square of the irradiance).

Table 2. Summary table for the LIS-A light source with the relative standard deviation of the irradiance (from photodiode) and of the spectroradiometer response, for the different configurations and integration times.

Integration time / s	Period / s	Standard deviation of the irradiance	Standard deviation of the spectroradiometer response (580 nm)	Standard deviation of the spectroradiometer response (470 nm – 700 nm)
1,5	0	0,001%	0,015%	0,01%
	1	0,011%	0,010%	0,01%
		0,10%	0,03%	0,02%
		0,98%	0,15%	0,15%
	2	0,01%	0,02%	0,01%
		0,10%	0,03%	0,03%
		0,98%	0,26%	0,26%
	4	0,01%	0,01%	0,01%
		0,10%	0,08%	0,08%
		0,98%	0,77%	0,77%
	8	0,01%	0,02%	0,01%
		0,10%	0,09%	0,09%
0,98%		0,95%	0,94%	
3,0	0	0,003%	0,021%	0,021%
	1	0,011%	0,014%	0,011%
		0,10%	0,03%	0,01%
		0,98%	0,02%	0,02%
	2	0,01%	0,02%	0,01%
		0,10%	0,03%	0,02%
		0,98%	0,27%	0,27%
	4	0,01%	0,02%	0,01%
		0,10%	0,04%	0,03%
		0,98%	0,42%	0,42%
	8	0,01%	0,02%	0,01%
		0,10%	0,08%	0,08%
0,98%		0,81%	0,80%	
5,6	0	0,002%	0,012%	0,012%
	1	0,011%	0,015%	0,011%
		0,10%	0,01%	0,02%
		0,99%	0,08%	0,11%
	2	0,01%	0,01%	0,01%
		0,10%	0,02%	0,01%
		0,98%	0,06%	0,08%
	4	0,01%	0,02%	0,01%
		0,10%	0,02%	0,01%
		0,98%	0,04%	0,04%
	8	0,01%	0,01%	0,01%
		0,10%	0,02%	0,01%
0,98%		0,05%	0,04%	

Figure 32: (LIS-A) Relative standard deviation of the responses is represented as a function of the ratio between the period of the irradiance and the integration time used by the spectroradiometer (580 nm).

Figure 33: (Top) Normalized spectral power distribution (SPD) of the spectral irradiance of LIS-A. (Bottom) Relative standard deviation of the response of the spectroradiometer, for no modulated irradiance.

In order to rule out a possible dependence on the light source in this analysis, the same methodology was followed for NICHIA NLSW30S01A. In this case, a Peltier controller was used to keep the Platinum RTD temperature at 90°C. The supply current was limited to a maximum of $I_{\max} = 200$ mA (limit of voltage of 47.5 V).

In Figure 28, it is shown the relative variation of the irradiance with respect to the supply current. The coefficient of sensitivity is 7.77 A^{-1} , calculated as the slope of the data represented in the figure.

In this case, periods, P , of 0 s, 1 s, 2 s, 4 s and 8 s and relative standard deviations, σ_r , of 0.001 and 0.0001 were selected, at two integration times 2.5 s and 5.5 s. The results for NICHIA are shown in Table 3, and Figure 35 and Figure 36.

Figure 34: Relative variation of the irradiance with respect to the supply current, for the Nichia light source.

Table 3. Summary table for the NICHA light source with the relative standard deviation of the irradiance (from photodiode) and of the spectroradiometer response, for the different configurations and integration times.

Integration time / s	Period / s	Standard deviation of the irradiance	Standard deviation of the spectroradiometer response (650 nm)	Standard deviation of the spectroradiometer response (393 nm – 700 nm)	
2,5	0	0,006%	0,014%	0,014%	
	1	0,014%	0,015%	0,005%	
		0,11%	0,02%	0,01%	
	2	0,01%	0,02%	0,008%	
		0,11%	0,03%	0,02%	
	4	0,01%	0,02%	0,006%	
		0,11%	0,05%	0,05%	
	8	0,02%	0,03%	0,02%	
		0,11%	0,09%	0,10%	
	5,5	0	0,01%	0,022%	0,022%
		1	0,01%	0,027%	0,009%
			0,11%	0,04%	0,01%
2		0,01%	0,02%	0,008%	
		0,112%	0,045%	0,013%	
4		0,014%	0,023%	0,008%	
		0,11%	0,04%	0,03%	
8		0,01%	0,04%	0,009%	
		0,11%	0,06%	0,06%	

Figure 35: (NICHIA) Relative standard deviation of the responses is represented as a function of the ratio between the period of the irradiance and the integration time used by the spectroradiometer (650 nm).

Figure 36: (Top) Normalized spectral power distribution (SPD) of the spectral irradiance of LIS-A. (Bottom) Relative standard deviation of the response of the spectroradiometer, for no modulated irradiance.

4. Discussion and conclusions

There are some conclusions that can be drawn from Table 2.

For a period of 0 s (no modulated irradiance), a relative standard deviation of the measured irradiance of between **0.001 %** and **0.003 %** was observed, which mainly includes the noises of the photodiode and LIS-A. In the case of the response of the spectroradiometer, these relative standards deviations are around 10 times higher (from **0.012 %** to **0.021 %**). The conclusion is that this variation is dominated by the noise of the spectroradiometer. **Therefore, it can be said that any relative variation of the light source much lower than 0.01 % won't increase significantly the error in the calibration of this instrument.**

The second conclusion that can be drawn consistently from Table 2 is that larger integration times and lower periods favors the increase of the SNR in the response of the spectroradiometer. The larger the ratio integration time / period, the larger the SNR.

It is found in general that the response of the spectroradiometer present is lower than the relative variation of the irradiance, save when the latter is lower than 0.01 %.

In Table 2, the relative standard deviations of the spectroradiometer responses for 580 nm and for the spectrally-integrated value (470 nm – 700 nm) are very similar. It indicates **that the dominant noise of the responses at different wavelengths is correlated, affecting all the wavelengths in the same way. The noise cannot be decreased by spectral integration.** One possible explanation might be in the accuracy in realizing the integration time in each acquisition, that is used internally for calculating the final response of the spectroradiometer. Note that the integration time returned by the spectroradiometer provide only four significant digits, and that when this is irradiated with an irradiance with a stability of 0.01 %, the variation of the internally selected values of integration time is 0.85 %.

These conclusions can be supported theoretically as it follows:

Given a modulation of the irradiance as:

$$E = E_{\max} \frac{[1 - B \cos(2\pi(t - t_0)/P)]}{(1 + B)} \quad (2)$$

where t_0 is initial time, and B is relative amplitude of the irradiance.

The standard deviation of the temporally-integrated response during an integration time t_{int} , can be expressed as:

$$H = \frac{H_{\max}}{(1 + B)} \int_0^{t_{\text{int}}} [1 - B \cos(2\pi(t - t_0)/P)] dt \quad (3)$$

$$H = \frac{H_{\max}}{(1 + B)} \left[t_{\text{int}} - \frac{BP}{2\pi} \sin(2\pi\Delta t/P) \right] \quad (4)$$

with $\Delta t = t_{\text{int}} - t_0$.

The relative deviation of H can be expressed as:

$$\Delta_r H = \frac{H - H(\Delta t = 0)}{H(\Delta t = 0)} = -\frac{BP}{2\pi t_{\text{int}}} \sin(2\pi\Delta t/P) \quad (5)$$

The relative standard deviation of H is obtained as:

$$\sigma_{H,\text{rel}} = \text{std}(\Delta_r H) = \frac{BP}{2\pi t_{\text{int}}} \text{std}[\sin(2\pi\Delta t/P)] \quad (6)$$

$$\sigma_{H,\text{rel}} = \left(\frac{B}{2\sqrt{2}\pi} \right) \times \left(\frac{P}{t_{\text{int}}} \right) \quad (7)$$

The relative standard deviation of the response of the spectroradiometer (σ_{rel}) would need to add the relative variation due to its noise ($\sigma_{\text{SP,rel}}$), as:

$$\sigma_{\text{rel}} = \sqrt{\sigma_{\text{SP,rel}}^2 + \sigma_{H,\text{rel}}^2} = \sqrt{\sigma_{\text{SP,rel}}^2 + \left(\frac{B}{2\sqrt{2}\pi} \right)^2 \times \left(\frac{P}{t_{\text{int}}} \right)^2} \quad (8)$$

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22IEM05 NEWSTAND

28 November 2025

Good practice guide

Use of the prototype sources for the near-infrared spectral range

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1. Scope

This Good Practice Guide describes the design, specifications, operating conditions, and limitations of the developed sources for the near-infrared spectral range.

2. Definitions

Dissemination of the (spectral) irradiance: A procedure allowing the comparison of (spectral) irradiance measurements with a measurement standard representing the (spectral) irradiance quantity.

Infrared (IR) radiation: Optical radiation for which the wavelengths are longer than those for visible radiation. For infrared radiation, the range between 780 nm and 1 mm is commonly subdivided into:

IR-A: 780 nm to 1400 nm;

IR-B: 1.4 μm to 3.0 μm ;

IR-C: 3 μm to 1 mm

(see 17-21-004 in [CIE S 017:2020]).

According to ISO 20473:2007, near-infrared (NIR) radiation includes the IR-A and IR-B spectral range, i.e., 780 nm to 3000 nm. The IR-C spectral range is divided into mid-infrared (MIR; 3 μm to 50 μm) and far-infrared (FIR; 50 μm to 1 mm).

Irradiance: Density of incident radiant flux with respect to area at a point on a real or imaginary surface, $E_e = d\Phi_e/dA$, where Φ_e is the radiant flux and A is the area on which the radiant flux is incident. The irradiance is expressed in W m^{-2} (see 17-21-053 in [CIE S 017:2020]).

Measurement standard: Realisation of the definition of a given quantity, with stated quantity value and associated measurement uncertainty, used as a reference (see 5.1 in [JCGM 200:2012]).

Primary standard: Measurement standard established using a primary reference measurement procedure, or created as an artefact, chosen by convention (see 5.4 in [JCGM 200:2012]). For (spectral) irradiance primary standards are represented by blackbody radiators, synchrotron radiation or cryogenic radiometers.

Realisation of the (spectral) irradiance quantity: Procedure allowing either (1) producing a well determined (spectral) irradiance, or (2) to determine the (spectral) irradiance on a specific plane. The case (1) is usually based on radiant sources, while the case (2) is based on detectors.

Spectral irradiance: Density of irradiance, $E_e(\lambda)$, with respect to wavelength, λ : $E_{e,\lambda} = dE_e(\lambda)/d\lambda$. The spectral irradiance is expressed in $\text{W m}^{-2} \text{nm}^{-1}$ (see 17-21-056 in [CIE S 017:2020]).

Transfer standard: Standard whose quantities are determined by measurements (calibration) traceable to a primary standard, and which allows the relevant quantity to be transferred.

3. Source based on red LEDs and IR phosphors

3.1. Design description

The source is based on a LED board by Intelligent LED Solutions (ILC-ONA7-RDOR-SC201-WIR200), which consists of seven OSRAM OSOLON™ SSL 80 LEDs (GA CS8PM1.23), electrically connected in series. Each LED chip is packaged with a silicone lens to reduce the half-value angle to typically less 40°.

The LED board is integrated in an aluminium housing, which hosts phosphors developed and deployed by PhosphorTech Corporation. Two different phosphors, both emitting mainly in the IR-A spectral range, are combined in the housing, but are spatially separated. Three LEDs are used to excite the shorter-wavelength phosphors and four LEDs for the longer-wavelength phosphors. The spatial arrangement is chosen to be symmetric around the centre of the housing for each type of phosphor.

To achieve stable and repeatable operating conditions, the aluminium housing is placed on a thermoelectric cooler (Arroyo Instruments 286-01 TECMount) which cools both, the LED board and the aluminium housing containing the phosphors. A graphite sheet is used between the TEC's thermal plate and the source to ensure high thermal conductivity.

The different components of the source are shown in Figure 1 and a photo of the source in operation is depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Drawing of the source based on seven LEDs and two different phosphors (short- and long-wavelength) emitting in the IR-A spectral range.

Figure 2: Picture of the source.

3.2. Specifications

The dimensional drawings of the source mounted on the thermoelectric cooler (TEC) are shown in Figure 3. The phosphors are held inside cylindrical holes of 5 mm diameter inside the aluminium housing and are excited by the LEDs behind them.

Figure 3: Drawing of the source mounted on the cold plate of the TEC (lengths in mm).

Figure 4: Linear plot of the spectral irradiance of the source at a distance of 300 mm.

Figure 5: Logarithmic plot of the source's spectral irradiance at a distance of 300 mm compared to spectral irradiance of a FEL 1000 lamp measured at a distance of 700 mm.

The measured spectral irradiance of the source, measured at a distance of 300 mm, is shown in Figure 4. In Figure 5, the same source's spectrum at 300 mm is shown on a logarithmic scale together with the spectrum of a FEL 1000 lamp, measured at a distance of 700 mm. Clearly, the two different spectral irradiances (at different measurement distances) differ between 2 and 3 orders of magnitude, see 3.5 Limitations for more details.

The residual transmitted light of the LED with a peak wavelength of 625 nm is dominant. At 710 nm, the spectral irradiance from the short-wavelength phosphor peaks at $2.3 \text{ mW m}^{-2} \text{ nm}^{-1}$ and continuously decreases into the infrared spectral range, until it reaches $0.2 \text{ mW m}^{-2} \text{ nm}^{-1}$ at 1150 nm. The emission of the long-wavelength phosphor mainly covers the spectral interval between 1200 nm and 1350 nm (above $0.4 \text{ mW m}^{-2} \text{ nm}^{-1}$) with an additional minor peak at 1450 nm (max. $0.1 \text{ mW m}^{-2} \text{ nm}^{-1}$).

3.3. Safety and handling instructions

To prevent the source from damage, the following handling instructions must be respected:

- The source is meant for operation in laboratory conditions and should not be used in other environments.
- The source should only be moved or adjusted when switched off.
- Current to the LEDs must not be applied when the TEC is inactive.
- An external, current-limited power supply must be used. The applied forward LED current must not exceed 1000 mA.
- No reverse bias should be applied to the LEDs.
- The source must not be exposed to liquids, moisture, dust or flames.

3.4. Operating conditions

Environment

Conditions with ambient temperature between 20 °C and 30 °C and relative humidity between 30 % and 70 % are recommended.

Thermoelectric cooling

For reproducibility, the TEC should be always operated at the same temperature (25 °C recommended) and large gradients between the TEC and the ambient temperature should be avoided. The linear temperature dependence of the LED's centroid wavelength is approximately 0.14 nm °C⁻¹ and the LED's radiant flux changes by approximately - 0.4 % °C⁻¹ around the TEC temperature of 25 °C for a fix LED forward current of 700 mA.

Electrical parameters

The seven LEDs must be operated with an external constant current source and should be switched on only when the TEC is active. The forward current range is 150 mA to 1000 mA, however, the source is designed to be operated at 700 mA. At the recommended forward current, the forward voltage drop is expected to be less than 18 V.

Alignment and reference plane

For alignment purposes, the source has a dust protection cap with a cross-hair at its centre. It can be used to align the input optics of the detector by means of a laser. A mirror can be placed on the cap to observe the reflected laser beam. The reference plane for the distance setting is the outer plane of the source's aluminium housing, see Figure 3. Due to the limited output of the source, a measurement distance of 300 mm from the reference plane is recommended.

Spatial homogeneity

Due to the short measurement distance and the relatively large effective area of the source, the spatial homogeneity at the measurement plane is not ideal, see 3.5 Limitations. Hence, a correction factor needs to be determined and applied for different input optics diameters.

Temporal stability

A warm-up time of 48 h should be allowed (see 3.5 Limitations).

Before the first use, the source should be seasoned for at least 1000 h and the output monitored in regular intervals.

3.5. Limitations

Non-ideal spatial homogeneity

A measurement of the relative spatial irradiance distribution is shown in Figure 6. As can be seen from the figure, the non-ideal homogeneity at a measurement distance of 300 mm from the source requires correction, which can be obtained from the characterisation measurement. As an example, the correction factors, $f_{\text{hom,corr.}}$, for a characterised source are given in Table 1. The correction factor is calculated relatively to a detector with an input optics diameter of $D = 12$ mm. The measurement uncertainty is estimated by the standard deviation calculated from 5 positions in the measurement plane: in the centre ($x = y = 0$ mm), 1 mm left/right and 1 mm up/down from the centre.

Figure 6: Homogeneity at a distance of 300 mm. Correction factors for different input optics diameters of the detectors can be calculated from this characterisation.

Detector diameter, D / mm	Homogeneity correction factor, $f_{\text{hom,corr.}}$	Standard uncertainty ($k = 1$)
10	0.998 17	0.000 08
15	1.003 48	0.000 11
20	1.011 45	0.000 20
25	1.022 55	0.000 21
30	1.037 24	0.000 18

Table 1: Example for correction factors, $f_{\text{hom,corr.}}$, to account for the non-ideal homogeneity at a measurement distance of 300 mm. As reference, a detector with an input optics diameter of $D = 12$ mm is taken.

Figure 7: Ratio of spectral irradiances between the newly developed source measured at 300 mm, $E_{e,\lambda}$, and a FEL 1000 transfer standard lamp at 700 mm, $E_{e,\lambda}$ (FEL 1000).

Figure 8: Temporal stability. The source has been off for 1 week before switch-on. After 124 h, the source was switched off 14 h and then switched on again. The integrated spectral irradiance values, $E_e(t)$, are normalised to the values attained after 475 h, $E_e(t = 475 \text{ h})$.

Low spectral irradiance levels and limited spectral coverage

The main limitation of the newly developed source is the low irradiance level and the limited spectral coverage, mainly emitting radiation only in the IR-A spectral range. For comparison with a FEL 1000 transfer standard lamp, the ratio of the spectral irradiance is shown in Figure 7. As can be seen in the figure, the spectral irradiance of the newly developed source at 300 mm reaches only 0.08 % to 2.3 % of the FEL 1000 lamp measured at 700 mm between 710 nm and 1510 nm. Moreover, the developed source shows unwanted

spectral features around 1185 nm and 1405 nm, most likely originating from absorption in the host material of the deposited long-wavelength phosphor.

Commercially available infrared phosphors, which would lead to higher irradiance levels, larger spectral coverage and a smoother spectrum, have not been found during project NEWSTAND.

Temporal drift

The measurement in Figure 8 shows the temporal stability of the source. Before the measurement, the LEDs have been seasoned for 1000 h, whereof 250 h together with the phosphors. While the LEDs quickly reach a stable output after switching on the source, the output of the phosphors tends to drift over an extended period of time. After a warm-up time of 48 h, the output of the short-wavelength phosphor (below 1150 nm) reaches 99.5 % of its nominal value with a drift of less than +0.007 %/h. The long-wavelength phosphor (above 1200 nm) tends to be less stable and only reaches 97 % of its nominal output with a drift of less than +0.05 %/h. After interrupting the source for 14 h, the phosphor's output falls back to a lower level and slowly starts to increase again. The origin of this behaviour is not understood yet.

The issue of temporal drift, together with the low spectral irradiance levels and limited spectral coverage, prevents the source from serving as a reliable transfer standard for disseminating the spectral irradiance quantity.

4. Sources based on IR LEDs

4.1. Design description

Two prototype sources have been produced within the scope of the project. The *RISE-Fiber* and the *RISE-LED* sources were developed and used in the project intercomparison.

4.1.1. RISE-Fiber

The RISE-Fiber source is based on high-power LEDs from Thorlabs, each with a drive current between 800 mA and 1000 mA. The LEDs are mounted in heat-sunk encapsulation and prepared for coupling of the radiation into an optical fibre, providing a relatively stable operating condition, see Figure 9.

Figure 9: Commercially available fibre-coupled LED, used for the RISE-Fiber source. Picture from Thorlabs.

In order to combine the radiation from several LEDs, a fibre bundle is used, also available from Thorlabs. The fibre bundle uses 7 individual fibres which are combined side-by-side at the output end, see Figure 10.

Figure 10: Commercially available fibre-bundle, used for the RISE-Fiber source. Picture from Thorlabs.

The fibres are connected using standard fibre-optic SMA connectors which simplifies the use. The output is also a fibre connector, see Figure 11. The radiation is directly available from the connector, or a patch cable could be used to bring the radiation to a more suitable position.

Figure 11: Fibre-bundle common output, showing the 7 fibre ends. Picture from Thorlabs.

4.1.2. RISE-LED

The RISE-LED source is based on standard infrared LED components which are commercially available. For RISE-LED, components with an incorporated lens were used. Each component was in either a TO-46 or TO-18 package, see Figure 12.

Figure 12: LED components used for RISE-LED source. Picture from Thorlabs.

The LED components were placed side-by-side using a standard circuit board. They were connected together according to their required drive current so that LEDs using the same drive current were connected in series, with a maximum of 5 LEDs in series. In total, 21 LEDs were used in the wavelength range from 780 nm to 1100 nm (centre wavelength).

In order to stabilise the temperature of RISE-LED, a thermally conducting epoxy was used to encapsulate the individual components, as seen in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Image of the lit source RISE-LED, showing the thermally conducting epoxy (grey).

A heater wire was also added to the epoxy which may be used to regulate the operating temperature to a temperature slightly above the temperature achieved when running the LEDs. A simple temperature controller with an on/off functionality and an embedded NTC resistor was used for this purpose.

4.2. Specifications

4.2.1. RISE-Fiber

The components used to assemble the source are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. RISE-Fiber source components.

Item	Manufacturer/Supplier	Data
M780F2	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (780 ± 10) nm Bandwidth 28 nm (typ.) 800 mA maximum drive current 16 mW optical power (in 600 µm fibre) 1600 mW electrical power consumption
M810F3	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (810 ± 10) nm Bandwidth 30 nm (typ.) 1000 mA maximum drive current 33 mW optical power (in 600 µm fibre) 3600 mW electrical power consumption
M850F3	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (850 ± 10) nm Bandwidth 30 nm (typ.) 1000 mA maximum drive current 33 mW optical power (in 600 µm fibre) 3200 mW electrical power consumption
M880F2	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (880 ± 10) nm Bandwidth 50 nm (typ.) 1000 mA maximum drive current 7.8 mW optical power (in 600 µm fibre) 1700 mW electrical power consumption
M940F3	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (940 ± 10) nm Bandwidth 60 nm (typ.) 1000 mA maximum drive current 30 mW optical power (in 600 µm fibre) 3800 mW electrical power consumption

Table 2. RISE-Fiber source components.

Item	Manufacturer/Supplier	Data
M970F3	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (970 ± 10) nm Bandwidth 60 nm (typ.) 1000 mA maximum drive current 16 mW optical power (in 600 µm fibre) 1900 mW electrical power consumption
M1100F1	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (1100 ± 50) nm Bandwidth 50 nm (typ.) 1000 mA maximum drive current 10 mW optical power (in 600 µm fibre) 1800 mW electrical power consumption
BF76LS01	Thorlabs	Fanout bundle, 7 fibres (FT600EMT) 600 µm core, low-OH fibre Numerical Aperture (NA): 0.39 (400 to 2200) nm SMA connectors 1 m total length
SLC-MA12-U	Mightex	12-channel LED Driver USB computer control 1 mA resolution 1000 mA maximum current

The source is normally driven with the settings according to Table 3.

Table 3. RISE-Fiber source drive settings.

LED	Drive current I_{max} / %
M780F2	60
M810F3	50
M850F3	50
M880F2	100
M940F3	60
M970F3	100
M1100F1	80

The setting in Table 3 renders the spectral content shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Spectral irradiance, $E_{e,\lambda}$, of the RISE-Fiber source at 10 cm distance from connector end-face.

The figure shows the measured irradiance, however, it is limited by the spectrometer sensitivity near 1100 nm. Also, the centre wavelength of the 1100 nm LED is most likely between 1100 nm and 1150 nm.

The uniformity of the source has not been explicitly measured, but it is indicated by Figure 15.

Figure 15: Image of the RISE-Fiber source irradiance distribution at 10 cm distance from connector end-face.

The picture shows the illumination on a millimetre-scale paper placed 10 cm from the connector end-face. A usable area of at least 30 mm in diameter is feasible, as indicated by the red circle.

The entire RISE-Fiber source is shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Image of the RISE-Fiber source. Inset shows the connector end-face.

4.2.2. RISE-LED

The components used to assemble the source are listed in Table 4.

Table 4. RISE-LED source components.

Item	Manufacturer/Supplier	Data
LED780L	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (780 ± 20) nm Bandwidth 25 nm (typ.) 75 mA maximum drive current 33 mW optical power
LED800L	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (800 ± 20) nm Bandwidth 30 nm (typ.) 75 mA maximum drive current 30 mW optical power
LED810L	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (810 ± 20) nm Bandwidth 30 nm (typ.) 75 mA maximum drive current 33 mW optical power
LED830L	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (830 ± 20) nm Bandwidth 32 nm (typ.) 75 mA maximum drive current 33 mW optical power
LED840L	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (840 ± 20) nm Bandwidth 35 nm (typ.) 75 mA maximum drive current 33 mW optical power
LED870L	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (870 ± 20) nm Bandwidth 25 nm (typ.) 75 mA maximum drive current 33 mW optical power
LED890L	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (890 ± 20) nm Bandwidth 44 nm (typ.) 75 mA maximum drive current 18 mW optical power
LED910L	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (910 ± 20) nm Bandwidth 44 nm (typ.)

Table 4. RISE-LED source components.

Item	Manufacturer/Supplier	Data
		75 mA maximum drive current 33 mW optical power
LED930L	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (930 ± 20) nm Bandwidth 60 nm (typ.) 75 mA maximum drive current 22 mW optical power
365-1579-ND	DigiKey	Centre wavelength 935 nm Bandwidth 80 nm (typ.) 100 mA maximum drive current 5 mW optical power
LED940E	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength 940 nm Bandwidth 50 nm (typ.) 100 mA maximum drive current 6 mW optical power Ø 5 mm epoxy casing
TSTS7100-ND	DigiKey	Centre wavelength 950 nm Bandwidth 30 nm (typ.) 100 mA maximum drive current 17 mW optical power
LED970L	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (970 ± 20) nm Bandwidth 46 nm (typ.) 75 mA maximum drive current 33 mW optical power
EOLD-980-015-1	DigiKey	Centre wavelength (980 ± 20) nm Bandwidth 46 nm (typ.) 100 mA maximum drive current 23 mW optical power
1125-1415-ND (2X)	DigiKey	Centre wavelength (1020 ± 20) nm Bandwidth 50 nm (typ.) 100 mA maximum drive current 20 mW optical power 2 LEDs used
LED1050L	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (1050 ± 50) nm Bandwidth 50 nm (typ.) 100 mA maximum drive current 8 mW optical power
1125-1498-ND	DigiKey	Centre wavelength 1070 nm Bandwidth 74 nm (typ.) 100 mA maximum drive current 24 mW optical power
LED1070L	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (1070 ± 20) nm Bandwidth 55 nm (typ.) 100 mA maximum drive current 8 mW optical power
LED1085L	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (1085 ± 20) nm Bandwidth 50 nm (typ.) 100 mA maximum drive current 10 mW optical power
5242-EOLD- 1100-015-1-ND	DigiKey	Centre wavelength (1100 ± 20) nm Bandwidth 57 nm (typ.) 100 mA maximum drive current 24 mW optical power

The source is normally driven with the settings according to Table 5.

Table 5. RISE-LED source drive settings.

LED	Driver circuit no.	Drive current I / mA
LED780L	1	70
LED800L	2	50
LED810L	2	50
LED830L	2	50
LED840L	2	50
LED870L	1	70
LED890L	1	70
LED910L	3	75
LED930L	3	75
365-1579-ND	8	100
LED940E	4	70
TSTS7100-ND	5	20
LED970L	6	50
EOLD-980-015-1	6	50
1125-1415-ND	4	70
LED1050L	4	70
1125-1498-ND	4	70
LED1070L	7	60
LED1085L	7	60
EOLD-1100-015	7	60

The setting in Table 5 renders the spectral content shown in Figure 17.

Figure 17: Spectral irradiance, $E_{e,\lambda}$, of the RISE-LED source at 30 cm distance from the source circuit board surface.

Due to the much larger source size, it is necessary to use the source at 30 cm distance. The uniformity of the source has not been explicitly measured but it is indicated by Figure 18.

Figure 18: Image of the RISE-LED source irradiance distribution at 30 cm distance from source surface.

The picture shows the illumination on a millimetre-scale paper placed 30 cm from the source. A usable area of at least 40 mm in diameter is feasible, as indicated by the red circle.

The entire RISE-LED source is shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19: Image of the RISE-LED source. Right picture is obtained with an infrared-sensitive camera.

4.3. Safety and handling instructions

To prevent the source from damage, the following handling instructions must be respected:

- The source is meant for operation in laboratory conditions and should not be used in other environments.
- The source must not be exposed to liquids, moisture, dust or flames.

Particular for RISE-Fiber

- The source is powered by the incorporated LED driver box, which in turn is controlled by a LabView program on a USB-connected computer. In the software, the current can be regulated between 0 %

and 100 % of the maximum for each LED, meaning that it is safe to adjust anything from the software (LED-driver -4.vi).

Particular for RISE-LED

- The source is powered by the LED driver PCB. The currents are set using a trim-potentiometer on the PCB. Only 24 Vdc is required to be connected.
- The source has a temperature control PCB (+12 Vdc supply) which can be used to stabilise the temperature. Since only heating is possible, the set temperature must be higher than the temperature when the LEDs are lit, typically near +50 °C.
- Source is hot to the touch.

The sources have been assessed according to the standard for photobiological safety of lamps and lamp systems, EN IEC 62471:2006. The sources RISE-Fiber and RISE-LED are found to belong to the Exempt group of lamps, see results in Annex A Photobiological safety.

4.4. Operating conditions

Environment

Conditions with ambient temperature between 20 °C and 30 °C and relative humidity between 30 % and 70 % are recommended.

Thermal stability

For reproducibility, the sources shall be operated in stable laboratory conditions in terms of air flow and temperature.

Electrical parameters

The LEDs are driven by controlled LED drivers and should normally not require any adjustment.

Alignment and reference plane

The reference plane for RISE-Fiber is the end-face of the connector. For alignment purposes, distance and optical axis must be determined based on the connector symmetry. The recommended measurement distance is 100 mm.

The reference plane for RISE-LED is the circuit board surface. For alignment purposes, distance and optical axis must be determined based on the circuit board symmetry. The recommended measurement distance is 300 mm.

Spatial homogeneity

The irradiance spatial homogeneity has not been determined, but it is expected to handle entrance optics with diameters up to 30 mm to 40 mm at the measurement distance.

Spectral homogeneity

The spectral lateral homogeneity at the measurement distance has not been determined.

Temporal stability

A warm-up time of minimum 15 min should be allowed. Before the first use, the source should be seasoned for at least 100 h and the output monitored in regular intervals.

4.5. Limitations

The main limitations of the source in comparison with a standard QTH lamp are:

- Spectral variation of irradiance
- Irradiance spatial homogeneity
- Spectral lateral homogeneity
- Irradiance level is low

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Annex A Photobiological safety

The sources have been assessed according to the standard for photobiological safety of lamps and lamps systems, EN IEC 62471:2006.

The sources RISE-Fiber and RISE-LED are found to belong to the Exempt group of lamps. The assessment is based on measurement of radiation at 200 mm distance from the source and subsequent calculation of irradiance/radiance and comparison with exposure limits, see results in Figure 20 and Figure 21.

Summary of the exposure limits for the surface of the skin or cornea (irradiance based values)

Hazard name	Relevant equation	Wavelength range (nm)	Exposure duration (s)	Limiting aperture (rad) / (deg)	Exposure limit Exempt group (W/m ²)	Measurement value (W/m ²)
Actinic UV skin & eye	$E_S = \sum E_\lambda \cdot S_{UV}(\lambda)$	200 - 400	30000	1,4 / 80	N/A	N/A
Eye UV-A	$E_{UVA} = \sum E_\lambda \cdot \Delta\lambda$	315 - 400	1000	1,4 / 80	N/A	N/A
Blue-light small source	$E_B = \sum E_\lambda \cdot B(\lambda) \cdot \Delta\lambda$	300 - 700	10000	< 0.011	N/A	N/A
Eye IR	$E_{IR} = \sum E_\lambda \cdot \Delta\lambda$	780 - 3000	1000	1,4 / 80	101.2	2.5
Skin thermal	$E_H = \sum E_\lambda \cdot \Delta\lambda$	380 - 3000	10	2π sr	3557	3

Summary of the exposure limits for the retina (radiance based values)

Hazard name	Relevant equation	Wavelength range (nm)	Exposure duration (s)	Field of view (rad)	Exposure limit Exempt group (W/m ² /sr)	Measurement value (W/m ² /sr)
Blue light	$L_B = \sum L_\lambda \cdot B(\lambda) \cdot \Delta\lambda$	300 - 700	10000	0.1000	N/A	N/A
Retinal thermal	$L_R = \sum L_\lambda \cdot R(\lambda) \cdot \Delta\lambda$	380 - 1400	10	0.0110	2.56E+06	1.46E+04
Retinal thermal (weak visual stimulus)	$L_{IR} = \sum L_\lambda \cdot R(\lambda) \cdot \Delta\lambda$	780 - 1400	1000	0.011	5.45E+05	1.18E+04

Figure 20: Results for RISE-Fiber lamp, assessed at 200 mm distance according to requirements for Exempt Group in EN IEC 62471.

Summary of the exposure limits for the surface of the skin or cornea (irradiance based values)

Hazard name	Relevant equation	Wavelength range (nm)	Exposure duration (s)	Limiting aperture (rad) / (deg)	Exposure limit Exempt group (W/m ²)	Measurement value (W/m ²)
Actinic UV skin & eye	$E_S = \sum E_\lambda \cdot S_{UV}(\lambda)$	200 - 400	30000	1,4 / 80	N/A	N/A
Eye UV-A	$E_{UVA} = \sum E_\lambda \cdot \Delta\lambda$	315 - 400	1000	1,4 / 80	N/A	N/A
Blue-light small source	$E_B = \sum E_\lambda \cdot B(\lambda)$	300 - 700	10000	< 0.011	N/A	N/A
Eye IR	$E_{IR} = \sum E_\lambda \cdot \Delta\lambda$	780 - 3000	1000	1,4 / 80	101.2	25.2
Skin thermal	$E_H = \sum E_\lambda \cdot \Delta\lambda$	380 - 3000	10	2π sr	3557	26

Summary of the exposure limits for the retina (radiance based values)

Hazard name	Relevant equation	Wavelength range (nm)	Exposure duration (s)	Field of view (rad)	Exposure limit Exempt group (W/m ² /sr)	Measurement value (W/m ² /sr)
Blue light	$L_B = \sum L_\lambda \cdot B(\lambda) \cdot \Delta\lambda$	300 - 700	10000	0.1000	N/A	N/A
Retinal thermal	$L_R = \sum L_\lambda \cdot R(\lambda) \cdot \Delta\lambda$	380 - 1400	10	0.0110	2.81E+05	1.89E+04
Retinal thermal (weak visual stimulus)	$L_{IR} = \sum L_\lambda \cdot R(\lambda) \cdot \Delta\lambda$	780 - 1400	1000	0.011	6.00E+04	1.77E+04

Figure 21: Results for RISE-LED lamp, assessed at 200 mm distance according to requirements for Exempt Group in EN IEC 62471.

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Good practice guide

Use of the narrowband tuneable sources

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1. Scope

This Good Practice Guide describes the design, specifications, operating conditions, and limitations of the developed Compact Narrowband Tuneable Source (CNTS) for UV-VIS-NIR spectral range.

2. Definitions

Dissemination of the (spectral) irradiance: A procedure allowing the comparison of (spectral) irradiance measurements with a measurement standard representing the (spectral) irradiance quantity.

Irradiance: Density of incident radiant flux with respect to area at a point on a real or imaginary surface, $E_e = d\Phi_e/dA$, where Φ_e is the radiant flux and A is the area on which the radiant flux is incident. The irradiance is expressed in $W\ m^{-2}$ (see 17-21-053 in [CIE S 017:2020]).

Measurement standard: Realisation of the definition of a given quantity, with stated quantity value and associated measurement uncertainty, used as a reference (see 5.1 in [JCGM 200:2012]).

Primary standard: Measurement standard established using a primary reference measurement procedure, or created as an artefact, chosen by convention (see 5.4 in [JCGM 200:2012]). For (spectral) irradiance primary standards are represented by blackbody radiators, synchrotron radiation or cryogenic radiometers.

Realisation of the (spectral) irradiance quantity: Procedure allowing either (1) producing a well determined (spectral) irradiance, or (2) to determine the (spectral) irradiance on a specific plane. The case (1) is usually based on radiant sources, while the case (2) is based on detectors.

Spectral irradiance: Density of irradiance, $E_e(\lambda)$, with respect to wavelength, λ : $E_{e,\lambda} = dE_e(\lambda)/d\lambda$. The spectral irradiance is expressed in $W\ m^{-2}\ nm^{-1}$ (see 17-21-056 in [CIE S 017:2020]).

Transfer standard: Standard whose quantities are determined by measurements (calibration) traceable to a primary standard, and which allows the relevant quantity to be transferred.

3. Compact Narrowband Tuneable Source (CNTS)

3.1. Design description

The CNTS is a combination of a high intensity fibre coupled broadband laser driven light source (Horne, et al., 2010) and an optical tuneable dispersion system; the latter rejecting all but a narrow wavelength band. The optical layout was designed using Zemax, an important consideration in the design being that CNTS would be transportable thus enabling its use as an in-field source for irradiance calibrations.

The CNTS tuneable dispersion system is contained within a 400 mm x 400 mm optical board, with the grating and the second parabolic mirror positions fixed; and the input pinhole (PH1), the first parabolic mirror (OAPM1) and the output slit (PH2) mounted on high precision micro-metric linear stages to provide the fine adjustment needed to compensate for the focal length tolerance of the parabolic mirrors. Both parabolic mirrors and the gratings are mounted on adjustable stages to optimise the mirrors' optical alignment. A motorised rotation stage, which sets the grating angle, uses a high-resolution encoder that has an accuracy of better than 0.001° . To cover the whole spectral range of interest a set of three gratings (G1, G2 and G3) optimised for three adjacent spectral ranges is utilised in the system. The selection of gratings is actuated via dedicated motorised stage bearing a set of three independent fine adjustable grating holders allowing individual optical alignment. A motorised filter wheel (FW) is placed into the collimated part of the beam path to act as order sorting long-pass optical filters and as a shutter. A few optical buffers are placed to reduce the coupling of internal stray-light of the system to the output slit. The optical configuration of the CNTS is shown in Figure 1. The spectrally filtered optical radiation emerging from PH2 is subsequently collimated by the third off-axis parabolic mirror (OAPM3). This optical relay generates a spatially uniform, elliptical beam profile at the output plane, ensuring well-defined and homogeneous irradiance across the detector active areas.

Figure 1: Optical configuration of CNTS.

3.2. Specifications

The specifications listed below refer to the current configuration consisting of an output pinhole (PH2) with a diameter of $100\ \mu\text{m}$ and with a collimating off axis parabolic mirror (OAPM3) with a focal length of 150 mm and 25 mm aperture diameter. The irradiance level can be increased by using a larger output pinhole (e.g., $500\ \mu\text{m}$), though this comes at the cost of a broader full width at half maximum (FWHM). The optimal trade-off depends on the requirements of the spectrometer to be calibrated. The beam geometry is governed by the focal length and clear aperture of OAPM3. A shorter-focal-length off-axis parabolic mirror produces a smaller collimated beam with correspondingly higher irradiance at the detector plane. Conversely, increasing the mirror aperture and focal length yields a larger collimated beam with reduced irradiance. In this guide we report the

specifications relative to two gratings G1 and G2 that have been thoroughly tested during the development. Specification of the CNTS in the IR region will be added when the full characterisation will be completed.

Optical field geometry

The collimated optical field exhibits an elliptical profile with major and minor axes of 22 mm and 19 mm, respectively. The optical beam exhibits a divergence half-angle smaller than 0.1°.

Spectral range

The NFT is designed to operate over a spectral range from 320 nm to 1650 nm. To achieve this, the CNTS is equipped with three reflective gratings (G1, G2 and G3), each optimised for a specific band:

- G1 : UV–VIS: 350 nm to 700 nm
- G2 : VIS–NIR: 700 nm to 1050 nm
- G3 : NIR–IR: 1050 nm to 1650 nm

Grating G1 UV-VIS

The grating G1 is optimised to work in the UV VIS spectral range.

Grooves/mm	Spectral range /nm	FWHM /nm	Wavelength accuracy /nm
2400	320 to 700	0.2	< 0.1

The wavelength scale is calibrated using a set of Kr Laser lines measured with calibrated wavemeter. From the measured points the wavelength scale is extended using the grating model to fit the measured data the wavelength accuracy is better than 0.1 nm [Smid 2021, Smid 2023].

The CNTS irradiance output level is measured by a predictable quantum detector (PQED) (Müller, et al., 2013) equipped with a calibrated aperture.

Grating G2 VIS-NIR

Grooves/mm	Spectral range /nm	FWHM /nm	Wavelength accuracy /nm
1200	700 to 1050	0.4	< 0.2

Figure 2: Irradiance levels using G2.

Irradiance levels above 850 nm will require a InGaAs or Ge based irradiance standards currently under development.

Grating G3 IR

Grooves/mm	Spectral range /nm	FWHM /nm	Wavelength accuracy /nm
600	1050 to 1650	0.8	< 0.4

3.3. Operating conditions

Environment

Conditions with ambient temperature between 20 °C and 30 °C and relative humidity between 30 % and 70 % are recommended.

Alignment

Because the optical field is highly collimated, the irradiance remains largely unaffected by variations in position along the optical axis. Alignment on the plane perpendicular to the optical axis can be performed visually using the gratin zero order angle CNTS broadband brighter output beam.

Temporal stability

A warm-up time of 10 min should be allowed to stabilise the laser driven light source. After that period the temporal stability is better than 0.2 %.

Wavelength scale stability

The wavelength scale stability of the CNTS when it is not moved and in laboratory conditions has been measured to be better than 0.02 nm. In case of transportation the wavelength scale should be verified by coupling to the CNTS optical fibre to a laser of known wavelength.

Source control

Given the complex nature of the light machine the CNTS can be operated only using the developed LabView software.

3.4. Limitations

Non-ideal spatial homogeneity

The spatial homogeneity of the optical field was characterised using a small-area silicon photodiode (0.2 mm diameter) mounted on motorised stages enabling horizontal and vertical motion. The photodiode's photocurrent, converted to voltage, was recorded over a 25 mm × 25 mm square region centred on the illumination's geometric midpoint. The figure below shows the resulting optical field spatial distribution. The spatial uniformity around the central region is better than 3 %, except for a small area exhibiting reduced irradiance, likely caused by a local grating inhomogeneity that is currently under investigation.

Figure 3: CNTS spatial uniformity.

Irradiance levels

As mentioned earlier with an output pinhole (PH2) with a diameter of 100 μm and with a collimating off axis parabolic mirror (OAPM3) with a focal length of 150 mm and 25 mm aperture diameter the resulting CNTS irradiance levels are smaller than 1 mW m^{-2} . The irradiance level can be increased by using a larger output pinhole though this comes at the cost of a broader FWHM.

Stray Light

From the standpoint of the monochromatic purity of its optical output, the CNTS exhibits two spectral shoulders with an intensity of about 1 % relative to the peak. These shoulders extend symmetrically by approximately $\pm 6 \text{ nm}$ around the central wavelength. Therefore, when calibrating a spectrometer, the measured spectral irradiance should be integrated over a spectral interval of at least $\pm 6 \text{ nm}$ around the target wavelength to properly account for these contributions.

Figure 4: Measurement of CNTS spectral stray light with QASUME spectrometer.

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